

EVALUATION OF ANTIPYRETIC AND PLATELET AUGMENTATION ACTIVITY OF CHAMPAK AGAD – AN ANIMAL STUDY.

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Abstract:

In Agadtantra, different type of keeta are mentioned. Among all keeta Mahaska [mosquito] is one of them. Fever is the major symptom occurred after insect bite(malaria, dengue chickengunia)and thrombocytopenia is one of the pathological condition occurred in infected person. Agad Is poly herb mineral formulation which is vishaghna (antitoxic). Acharya Vagbhat has mentioned champak agad for the management of keeta visha poisoning.

Research studies of an individual drug of Champak Agad shows the antipyretic, antimalarial, antimicrobial and anti-virulence effect. It shows we can prove the synergist effect of all the drug may be effective in this study. The aim of this study is to evaluate the antipyretic and platelet augmentation activities of champak agad .

A total 42 albino wistar rat of an average weight of 180-220 grams will be used for this study. Antipyretic activity will be carried out by inducing pyrexia by injecting 10ml/kg of 20% suspension of dried Brewer's yeast in Normal saline subcutaneously. Temperature of each mouse will be determined rectally by thermometer

Platelet augmentation activity will be carried out by inducing thrombocytopenia by injecting cyclophosphamide subcutaneously. Platelet count RBC WBC HB % and clotting time will be determined by using hematological analyzer.

The result will be drawn from the observation of statistical test and biochemical parameters report. Considering viability, the formulation will be created which can then be ultimately used for social advantage.

Expected Results-Champak Agad may show the Antipyretic and platelet augmentation activity in Wistar rats.

Keywords-Keeta visha, Mashaka, Champak agad, Antipyretic, Platelet Augmentation, Thrombocytopenia.

MAIN MANUSCRIPT-

1. Introduction-

Ayurveda is an ancient Indian System of medicine having eight branches i.e. Ashtang Ayurved. Among them Agadtantra i.e. Danshrachikitsa i.e. Vishachikitsa i.e. Doctrine of Antidote is important pillar of Ashtang Ayurveda which deals with study of toxicological conditions and its management.[1]

It deals with the study of Animate and Inanimate poisoning (*Jangam* and *sthawar vish* resp.). In Ayurveda Samhitas Acharya has explained various types of 'Jangam Visha' (animate Poison) it includes, *Luta*, *Sarpa*, *Vrischika Keeta*, etc. which are responsible for life threatening condition in humans life.

According to Dosha there are four types of *Keeta* viz. *vataj*, *pittaj*, *kaphaj* and *sannipataj*. There common symptoms are *Shir akshi Gaurav*(heaviness in head and eyes), *Murchha*(Unconsciousness), *Bhrama*(giddiness), *Shwasa*(Breathlessness), *Ativedana*(Intense pain), *Jwara*(Fever), *Kandu*(Itching), *Arochaka*(Anorexia).[2]

Jwara is common symptom among all clinical features occurred after *Keeta visha* poisoning.

Among all *keeta*, five types of *mashaka* (mosquito) are explained with its clinical symptoms which includes severe itching, oedema and life threatening condition.

Keeta mentioned in Ayurveda along with its clinical symptoms and Insect mentioned in modern text with clinical symptoms are nearly similar. Mosquitoes are common vector for taking virulent micro-organism and passing them along to subsequent bite target.

Fever is one of the major symptom occurred after mosquito bite. (ex- Malaria, Chikungunya, Dengue etc.)[3] Along with clinical symptoms serological studies revealed hasty decline in patient's platelet count.[4] Diseases like malaria, chikungunya, dengue fever are responsible for the clustering of febrile thrombocytopenia condition after mosquito bite.[5]

In clinical features 'Acharya' have mentioned local symptoms and general systemic symptoms of *keeta visha* poisoning but there is no information about the specific blood component which

gets compromised. Hence there is no such evidence to correlate the *keeta visha* poisoning and Thrombocytopenia.

The management in thrombocytopenia in moderate or in severe condition with drugs or blood products is costly. Nevertheless due to certain side effects of drugs and cost, the availability of treatment is limited.

For *Keeta visha* poisoning management Acharya has explained several formulation which can be used as external and internal medication i.e. Agad. [6]

Agad are Poly herbal or Herbomineral drug preparation which is used in various types of poisoning. Agad have good prognostic value, many Ayurveda practitioners are using this Agad for treating the clinical condition created after *Keeta visha* poisoning.

In *Ashtang Hridayam*, Acharya Vagbhata has mentioned *Champak Agad* for the management of *keeta visha* poisoning. [7]

Though many Ayurveda practitioner's are using *Champak Agad* in fever along with thrombocytopenia condition and they are having good prognostic results, but because of lack of scientific evidences their efficacy is not proved.

So here this study is taken to prove the efficacy of the '*Agad dravya*' mentioned in *keeta visha* (*Mashaka*) poisoning.

According to Ayurveda, the individual drug of *Champak agad* has significant activity as a *raktastambhan* and *jwaraghna* (except *haridra* which has *raktshodhak* activity), and shows effect on Hematological disorder.

Research studies of an individual drug of Champak Agad shows the antipyretic, antimalarial, antimicrobial and anti-virulence effect. [8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18]

It shows that, we can prove the synergist effect of all the drugs may be effective in this study.

This study will help to increase the use of Ayurveda medicine in Management of fever with thrombocytopenia condition caused by mosquito bite. In future *Champak agad* study can be taken for clinical trial.

SR.NO	DRUG NAME	LATIN NAME	USEFUL PART	ACTIVITY
1.	Haridra	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Rhizome/Tuber	Antipyretic Antimicrobial Activity
2.	Daruharidra	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Root Bark	Antipyretic Antimicrobial Activity
3.	Patang	<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i>	Heart Wood	Antimicrobial Activity
4.	Manjishtha	<i>Rubia cardifolia</i>	Root	1.Antipyretic Study 2.Antiviral activity Against Rotavirus 3.Larvicidal & pupicidal activity against <i>Aedes aegypti</i>
5.	Tagar	<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>	Root/Tuber	Antipyretic Activity in Malaria fever
6.	Nagkeshar	<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	Stamens	Antivirulence Activity

RESEARCH STUDY	FINDINGS	RESEARCH GAP	PRAPOSED STUDY
<p>1.Ethnobotanical studies on <i>Berberis aristata</i> DC. root extracts M. Shahid1*, T. Rahim2, A. Shahzad3, Tajuddin2 African Journal of Biotechnology Vol. 8 (4), pp. 556-563, 18 February, 2009 ISSN 1684–5315 © 2009 Academic Journals</p>	<p>The aqueous extracts demonstrated significant antipyretic activity, which was present throughout the duration of the study, while the results for alcoholic extracts were non-significant in the later period.</p>	<p>Only single drug is tested for different parameter.</p>	<p>Along with other Drug ,this will be used for two parameter (antipyretic and thrombocytopenia) for synergist effect.</p>
<p>2.Anti-inflammatory and antipyretic activity of curcuma longa l. Collected from Uttarakhand . Neelam Arya, Om Prakash, Vivekanand and Pant, A. K. International Journal of Development Research. Vol. 5, Issue, 01, pp. 2914-2917, January, 2015.</p>	<p>Methanolic extract of <i>Curcuma longa</i> showed the maximum reduction in increased temperature.</p>	<p>Only single Drug is tested for two parameter.</p>	<p>Along with other Drug ,this will be used for two parameter (antipyretic and thrombocytopenia) for synergist effect.</p>
<p>3.Comparative study on effects of <i>Rubiae Radix et Rhizoma</i> and carbonized <i>Rubiae Radix et Rhizoma</i> On acute blood stasis rat model. Zhongguo Zhong Yao Za Zhi</p>	<p>CRRR achieved the main hemostatic mechanism by stimulating intrinsic and extrinsic blood coagulation and fibrinogen, and could significantly enhance the platelet aggregation rate of</p>	<p>In this study, The acute Blood stasis model was induced by s. c. injecting Adrenaline Hydrochloride. It's a single Drug study.</p>	<p>Thrombocytopenia will be established using Cyclophosphamide. Along with other Drug, this will be used for two parameter (antipyretic and</p>

. 2014 Feb;39(3):493-7[PUBMED]	rats in the acute blood stasis model.		thrombocytopenia) for synergist effect.
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- **AIM-** Evaluation of effect of *Champak Agad* as an Antipyretic and platelet augmentation in Thrombocytopenia in Wistar Rats.
- **OBJECTIVES-**
 1. To study the Antipyretic effect of *Champak Agad* in Brewer's yeast induced Pyrexia in Wistar rat.
 2. To study the platelet augmentation effect of *Champak agad* in cyclophosphamide induced Thrombocytopenia in Wistar rat.
 3. To study Hematological parameter of all group (platelet, RBC, WBC, Hb%, clotting time).
 4. To study the physicochemical and phytochemical parameter of *Champak Agad* in Wistar rat.

MATERIAL AND METHODS-

2.1 Plant Materials:-

Crude dried herbs of *Champak Agad* will be collected from Manas Ayurveda Pharmacy Nagpur. Authentication and Identification of Crude material will be done by the Expert of Dravyaguna or Botanist or FRLHT Bangluru.

Study of phytochemical and organoleptic properties of Champak Agad will be carried out at Central Research Lab DMIMS.

2.2 Preparation of *champak agad* -

Champak Agad choorna will be prepared at Dattatraya Rasashala, MGACH & RC, Salod (H) Wardha as per the reference of *Ashtang Hridayam*.

Sr.no.	Drug name	Latin name	Upayuktanga	Quantity
1.	Haridra	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Kanda (Dried)	250gm
2.	Daruharidra	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Mool/phal/kashtha/kanda(Dried)	250gm
3.	Patang	<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i>	Kashtha saar(Dried)	250gm
4.	Manjishtha	<i>Rubia cardifolia</i>	Kanda(Dried)	250gm
5.	Tagar	<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>	Mool moolstambha(Dried)	250gm
6.	Nagakeshar	<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	Punkeshar(Dried)	250gm

2.3 Animal Experimental Study

The experimental study will be designed to study Antipyretic and platelet augmentation activity of Champak Agad.

Study will be carried out as per guideline of CPCSEA (Committee for the Purpose Of Control and Supervision of Experiment on Animal) laboratory animals

A) Study Population

- Wistar Rat
- Animals of either sex will be selected

B) Grouping for Animal Study

1. Grouping for Evaluation of Antipyretic Activity

Sr. No.	Group Name	Intervention/ Drug
1.	Group A Normal Control	Animals will be treated with Normal Saline only. No intervention will be given.
2.	Group B Toxicant control	Animal will be treated with Dried Brewer's yeast
3.	Group C Standard	Animal will be treated with Dried Brewer's yeast and Paracetamol
4.	Group D Inducer	Animal will be treated with Dried Brewer's yeast and Test drug.

2. Grouping for Evaluation of Platelet Augmentation Activity

Sr.No.	Group Name	Intervention/ Drug
1.	Group A Normal Control	Animals will be treated with Normal Saline only. No intervention will be given.
2.	Group B Toxicant	Animal will be treated with Cyclophosphamide.
3.	Group C Standard	Animal will be treated with Cyclophosphamide and <i>Carica Papaya</i> leaf extract capsule
4.	Group D Inducer	Animal will be treated with Cyclophosphamide and Test drug.

2.4 Sample Size Determination-

Sample size is determined with the help of "Resource Equation" method.

This depends on Law of diminishing returns. It needs an estimation of E

$$E = (\text{Total number of experimental units}) - (\text{number of treatment group})$$

And should be between 10- 20

E is the number of Degrees of freedom in an analysis of Variance (ANNOVA) it is based

On the need to obtain an adequate estimate of the standard deviation. In present study

Treatment groups are 4 and if considered sample size 6 then $E=24-6 = 18$

E falls between 10-20 therefore 4 animals per group is acceptable. Considering the 20% dropout,

6 animal will be included in each group.

Animal species to be used	Wistar rats
Sex of animals to be used	50% males and 50% females (nulliparous) in Each group will be taken.
Average weight of animals	180-220 gm.
No. of animals	06 rats for each group
No. of groups	04 groups for each

2.5 Sampling Technique:

Simple Random Sampling.

2.6 Method of Selection of Study Subjects:

- Inclusion Criteria-

1. Healthy Wistar Rat.
2. Rats of either sex will be selected.

- Exclusion Criteria-

1. Infected Rats will be excluded from the study
2. Rats showing the sign of infection during the course of study

& those under other experiments will be excluded

3. Pregnant Wistar Rats will be excluded from the study.

2.7 Dose Fixation:

Champak agad dose-As per FDA dose calculation rule. [19]

$AED (mg / kg) = \text{Human does (mg / kg)} \times \text{Km ratio}$

For example, if the maximum dose of a particular drug in human is 10 mg/kg, The AED is calculated by multiplying the HED by 6.2 or dividing by 0.162; AED is 62 mg/kg. (AED- Animal equivalent Dose HED-Human equivalent Dose Km-correction factor)

2.8 Route of Administration:

Orally with the help of 2ml syringe.

2.9 Animal Experimental Study Design:

1. Evaluation of Antipyretic Activity of *Champak agad*-

Wistar Rats of either sex will be used for the study. They will be housed under standard condition of temperature and light and fed with standard diet and water.

The rectal temperature of each animal will be recorded by digital clinical thermometer before inducing Pyrexia. The Room temperature will remain constant during experiments.

Pyrexia will be produce by injecting 10ml/kg of 20% suspension of dried Brewer's yeast in

Normal saline subcutaneously on the back of Wistar rats 20hrs before performing the experiments.

The rectal temperature will be noted after 18hrs of developing pyrexia [20].

The Pyrexia will be noted at 30, 60, 90,120 min after administration of standard drug

Paracetamol and dose of *Champak Agad*.

SR.NO.	GROUP NAME	SAMPLE SIZE	INTERVENTION	ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION
1.	Normal Control	06	Saline water for 15 days	oral
2.	Toxicant Control	06	Brewer's yeast solution(20%) in normal saline10ml/kg	s.c.
3.	Standard Drug	06	Brewer's yeast solution(20%) in normal saline10ml/kg and Paracetamol 150mg/kg	s.c & oral
4.	Test Drug	06	Brewer's yeast solution(20%) in normal saline10ml/kg and <i>Champak agad</i> 310mg/kg	s.c. & oral

2. Evaluation of Platelet augmentation Activity of Champak agad

Wistar Rats of either sex will be used for the study. They will be housed under

Standard condition of temperature and light and fed with standard diet and water.

Thrombocytopenia will establish using cyclophosphamide. Freshly prepared cyclophosphamide

Solution will injected subcutaneously at dose of 50mg /kg for first Three days. Blood will be withdraw from Retro-orbital plexus on the day 1st, 4th, 7th 11th and 15th day of study after subjecting the animal to light anesthesia using ether.

Analysis of Hematological parameter (Platelet, RBC, WBC, HB count) of Rat blood will done

Using a Hematological analyzer. On the 15th day the clotting time of blood will determine by capillary method. [21]

SR.NO.	GROUP NAME	SAMPLE SIZE	INTERVENTION	ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION
1.	Normal control	06	Saline water for 15 days	oral
2.	Toxicant control	06	Cyclophosphamide (50mg/kg s.c.)for first three days	s.c. & oral
3.	Standard drug	06	Cyclophosphamide (50mg/kg s.c.)for first three days <i>Carica Papaya</i> leaf extract capsule of 400 mg for 15 days	s.c. & oral
4.	Test drug	06	Cyclophosphamide (50mg/kg s.c.)for first three days <i>Champak agad</i> 310mg/kg for 15 days	s.c. & oral

2.10 Screening Parameters: All animals will be screened for following parameters.

- a. Temperature will be noted at 30, 60, 90 and 120 min after administration of standard drug
PCM and graded dose of *Champak agad*.
- b. Platelet
- c. RBC
- d. WBC
- e. HB
- f. Clotting time

2.11 Method of Data Collection

All the group will be subjected for Hematological Analysis (Platelet, RBC, WBC, HB% and clotting time)

All the data will be collected by laboratory reports.

2.12 Data Analysis Method

All data management will be done in excel sheet. One way ANOVA followed by Tukey –Kramar Posttest

Will be apply for statistical analysis.

2.13 Expected Results-

Champak Agad may show the Antipyretic and platelet augmentation activity in Wistar rats.

3. DISCUSSION- Agad can be more specifically use in *Keeta Vishajanya* diseases.

After this study if we get the positive result we can use *Champak Agad* in Fever and Thrombocytopenia condition. Champak Agad will offers a potential therapeutic efficacy which will cost effective, more affordable and accessible treatment in patients having fever with Thrombocytopenia. If desired results occur it will generate new scope for Agad Dravya in management of Cellular component of blood.

Clinical study on *Champak agad* can also be done based on the results obtained after this Study completion.

Limitation of the study:

- The mechanism of induced Fever with Thrombocytopenia in animal is totally different from The Actual pathology of Fever with Thrombocytopenia in Human.
- However animal experiments are more important before doing the clinical studies in human.
- But clinical studies are needed to prove efficacy of drug as a proof evidence.
- So the limitation of this study is only in terms of Pre-clinical form.

4. CONCLUSION-

Fever with Thrombocytopenia condition after Mosquito bite (Dengue, Malaria, Chickengunya) is fatal. Conclusion will be drawn on the basis of effect of champak agad in antipyretic and platelet augmentation activity in wistar rats. Conclusion will be made on basis of Statistical Analysis and Biochemical parameters report.

CONSENT-

Not Applicable

ETHICAL APPROVAL-

Institutional Animal ethics committee approved the Protocol.

COMPETING INTERESTS-

No competing interest as declared by Author.

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